

THE DISTRIBUTION MODEL OF WHISKER ASPECT RATIO

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SUMMARY: An investigation was undertaken to appraise the aspect ratio (l/d) of whisker materials. The study on the whisker aspect ratio involves goodness-of-fit of aspect ratio distribution model and a statistical determination of an appropriate sample size. Four kinds of whiskers such as SiCw, Si₃N₄w and 9Al₂O₃·2B₂O₃w were used. The whisker figures were taken by scanning electron microscope and the whisker aspect ratios were measured from the SEM pictures. The results of goodness of fit test indicate that the whisker aspect ratio follows Logarithm-Normal distribution at 0.99 level of confidence. An appropriate sample size is found not to be smaller than 210.

KEYWORDS: whiskers, aspect ratio, distribution model, goodness-of-fit, sample size

INTRODUCTION

Discontinuous composites are an important class of materials which have potential for utilization in a wide variety of applications. The discontinuous reinforcement can be divided into three groups, short fiber, whisker and particulate, among them the whisker has been paid attention because of its distinct reinforcing effect in composites. In recent years, many kinds of whiskers have been produced and used as reinforcement [1-5]. Discontinuous composites have several advantages that are very important for their use as structural materials. A number of composite models have been developed over the last two decades with the aim of predicting the mechanical properties of composites for given data of constituent phases (matrix and reinforcement). For example, in the case of short fiber (whisker) metal matrix composites, the strength of an composite with variable fiber lengths can be predicated by[6]

$$\sigma_{uc} = \sum_{l_i < l_c} \tau_i (V_f)_i (l_i / d_i) + \sum_{l_j \geq l_c} \sigma_f (V_f)_j \left[1 - \frac{\sigma_f}{4\tau_i (l_j / d_j)} \right] + \sigma'_m (1 - V_f) \quad (1)$$

where σ_{uc} is the ultimate tensile strength of the short fiber composites, σ'_m is the flow stress of the matrix at the failure strain of the fiber, V_f is the volume fraction of the fiber, $(V_f)_i$ and $(V_f)_j$ are the volume fraction of the fibers with $l_i < l_c$ and those with $l_j \geq l_c$, respectively. l_c is the critical fiber length. τ_i is the matrix-fiber interfacial shear strength.

It is obvious that the strength of short fiber reinforced composites depends directly and strongly upon the aspect ratio (l/d) of the discontinuous reinforcement, and it is significant to evaluate carefully the short fiber (whisker) aspect ratio. Arsenault examined the non-uniformity of aspect ratio of SiC whisker and the percentage of whisker volume fraction at various aspect ratio [7]. Sakamoto analyzed the aspect ratio distribution using Weibull distribution [8]. But the problems dealing with whisker aspect ratio distribution has not been discussed fully, due mainly to it is relatively hard to measure a great number of the aspect ratio data required for analyzing statistically such a random variable as whisker aspect ratio.

EXPERIMENT

Whisker Materials

The whiskers used in this experiment were 1) β -SiCw (TWS-100) produced by Tokai Carbon Co.Ltd, 2) α -Si₃N₄w manufactured by Tateho Chemical Co.Ltd, 3) K₂O₆·TiO₂w (HT-300, Chitan Kogyo Co.Ltd) and 4) 9Al₂O₃·2B₂O₃w (Shikoku Chemical Co. Ltd).

Measuring Whisker Aspect Ratio

By means of mixing the as-received whiskers with clean water, stirring moderately the fluid in order to disperse the whiskers as well as do not damage them, trickling the mixed fluid on a clean Aluminium foil, the specimens with dispersive whiskers for observing under scanning electron microscope were prepared. The outward appearance of different whiskers are almost the same under the observation of SEM. Making the whiskers SEM photograph into slides, the images of whiskers were projected on a white background from which the diameter and length of whiskers were measured one by one.

Goodness-of-fit Test of Whisker Aspect Ratio Distribution

The aspect ratio data were drawn to distribution histograms. On the basis of the histogram shapes, the distribution models those whisker aspect ratio population maybe follows were tentatively estimated. Then, the maximum likelihood ratio test and Kolmogorov-Smirnov test were employed to determine how well the observed aspect ratio data "fit" the specified models.

Determining the Sample Sizes

Once the distribution model of whisker aspect ratio was statistically inferred, the characteristic numbers of whisker aspect ratio samples, such as the mathematical expectation (mean) and the variances, can be obtained to describe and better understand the aspect ratio of certain whisker. In general, more accurate results can be obtained with larger sample size. Since larger samples require more time, there may be a need for a trade-off between the sample size and the specific levels of precision.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Estimate of Distribution Models

The aspect ratio histograms of four kinds of whisker are shown in Figure 1. It can be found that the aspect ratio distribution is not symmetric. Comparing them with each other and with

Figure 1: Histograms of Whisker Aspect Ratio

the distribution density curves of various distribution models, two inferences can be made:

- The aspect ratio of different whiskers follow the same distribution model, and
- The distribution model may be LN-Normal and Weibull distribution.

On the basis of the first inference, any whisker, for example, the Silicon Carbide whisker, could be chosen to make goodness-of-fit test and the test result should be applicable for other whiskers.

Goodness-of-fit Test

Two types of goodness-of-fit methods are considered: “maximum likelihood ratio test” and “Kolmogorov-Smirnov test”. There is detailed knowledge in literature about the fundamental and the application of these test methods.

Maximum likelihood ratio test to distinguish between LN-Normal and Weibull distribution

$$\text{Hypotheses } H_0: f_0(x; \mu, \sigma) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma x} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{2\sigma^2}(\ln x - \mu)^2\right] \quad (x > 0) \quad (\text{LN-Normal})$$

that is, the whisker aspect ratio follows LN-Normal distribution

$$H_1: f_1(x; m, \eta) = \frac{m}{\eta} \left(\frac{x}{\eta}\right)^{m-1} \exp\left[-\frac{x}{\eta}\right] \quad (x > 0) \quad (\text{Weibull})$$

that is, the aspect ratio follows Weibull distribution

Test Statistic

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda &= \frac{\max_{m, \eta} \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{m}{\eta} \left(\frac{X_i}{\eta}\right)^{m-1} \exp\left[-\left(\frac{X_i}{\eta}\right)^m\right]}{\max_{\mu, \sigma} \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma X_i} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{2\sigma^2}(\ln X_i - \mu)^2\right]} \\ &= \frac{\left(\frac{\hat{m}}{\hat{\eta}}\right)^n \prod_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{X_i}{\hat{\eta}}\right)^{\hat{m}-1} \exp\left[-\left(\frac{X_i}{\hat{\eta}}\right)^{\hat{m}}\right]}{\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\hat{\sigma}}\right)^n \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{X_i} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{2\hat{\sigma}^2}(\ln X_i - \hat{\mu})^2\right]} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $\hat{\mu} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \ln X_i$, $\hat{\sigma}^2 = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (\ln X_i - \hat{\mu})^2$ are the maximum likelihood estimation of μ and σ^2 , respectively, \hat{m} , $\hat{\eta}$ are the maximum likelihood estimation of unknown parameters m , η in Weibull distribution respectively. Substituting the maximum likelihood estimations of μ , σ , m and η into Eqn 2, the test statistic λ could be simplified to

$$\lambda = (2\pi e \hat{\sigma}^2)^{\frac{n}{2}} \prod_{i=1}^n X_i f_1(X_i; \hat{m}, \hat{\eta}) \quad (3)$$

$$\text{If assuming } E = (2\pi e \hat{\sigma}^2)^{\frac{1}{2}} \left[\prod_{i=1}^n X_i f_1(X_i; \hat{m}, \hat{\eta}) \right]^{\frac{1}{n}} \quad (4)$$

thus “ $\lambda > K$ ” is equivalent to “ $E > K$ ”, and decision rule is

$$\begin{aligned} E > E_\alpha, & \text{ reject } H_0, \text{ accept } H_1 \\ E \leq E_\alpha, & \text{ reject } H_1, \text{ accept } H_0 \end{aligned}$$

Using the measured aspect ratio data of SiCw, the maximum likelihood estimations of μ , σ^2 , m and η can be computed respectively:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\mu} &= \frac{1}{50} \sum_{i=1}^{50} \ln x_i = 2.3712 & \hat{\sigma}^2 &= \frac{1}{50} \sum_{i=1}^{50} (\ln x_i - \hat{\mu})^2 = 0.5863 \\ \hat{m} &= 1.2739 & \hat{\eta} &= 11.28 \end{aligned}$$

where $x_i = l_i/d_i$. Substituting these estimation values into Eqn 4, the test statistic E is equal to 0.5715. For $\alpha=0.01$, $E_{0.01}=1.054$. Since $E = 0.5715 < E_{0.01} = 1.054$, the H_1 should be rejected at the 0.01 level of significance, or in other words, it should be appropriate to consider the whisker aspect ratio as following LN-Normal distribution.

Kolmogrov-Smirnov Test

In this investigation, the Kolmogrov-Smirnov Test was carried out by using a computer software of statistical inference. The test results indicate that the aspect ratio of four kinds of whisker follow LN-Normal distribution at the 0.99 level of confidence.

Determining the Sample Size Required for Evaluating Whisker Aspect ratio

It has been inferred that the whisker aspect ratio follow the LN-Normal distribution at a very high level of confidence. The researchers’ interest is focused on appraising truly the nature of whiskers using statistical parameters, for example, the means and the variances of whisker aspect ratio. According to the definition of LN-Normal distribution, if a random variable X follows a LN-Normal distribution (noted as $X \sim LN(\mu, \sigma^2)$), $\ln X$ follows a Normal distribution (noted as $\ln X \sim N(\mu, \sigma^2)$). The mathematic expectation (mean) and the variance of X are

$$E(X) = \exp\left(\mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2\right) \tag{5}$$

$$Var(X) = \exp[2\mu + \sigma^2][e^{\sigma^2} - 1] \tag{6}$$

where μ and σ^2 are the mean and the variance of Normal distribution population $\ln X$, respectively. Figure 2 shows the histogram of $\ln(l/d)$.

The Eqn 5 and 6 imply that the mean and the variance of LN-Normal population X depend on both mean and variance of Normal population $\ln X$. The problem of determining the sample size necessary to estimate σ^2 to within given tolerances and confidence levels is much complex. Triola gives the solution [9]:The sample variance s^2 is the best estimate of the population variance σ^2 . To be 95% confident that s^2 is within 20% of the value of σ^2 , the sample size n should be at least 210.

Figure 2: The histogram of $\ln(l/d)$

In terms of the means, the sample mean \bar{x} is the best point estimate of the population mean μ , and the sample size is given by

$$n = \left(\frac{Z_{\alpha/2} \sigma}{E} \right)^2 \tag{7}$$

where α is the level of significance, $Z_{\alpha/2}$ is the positive standard Z value that separates an area of $\alpha/2$ in the right tail of the standard normal distribution, σ is the standard deviation of normal distribution population and can be replaced by sample standard deviation s if $n > 30$, E is the maximum error of the point estimate \bar{x} .

The sample sizes necessary to estimate the mean and variance of whisker aspect ratio is determined according to follow schedule:

- 1) Taking the logarithm of whisker aspect ratio $(l/d)_i$.
- 2) Giving the level of confidence $1-\alpha=0.95$ ($\alpha=0.05$).
- 3) Determining the sample size n_{σ^2} for estimating the variance of $\ln(l/d)$, in this situation $n_{\sigma^2}=210$ as noted above.
- 4) Calculating the values of s^2 , s and \bar{x} with n_{σ^2} , here $s^2=0.556$, $s=0.746$ and $\bar{x} = 2.372$
- 5) For $\alpha = 0.05$, finding $Z_{\alpha/2} = 1.96$, assuming $E = 5\%$ $\bar{x} = 0.119$ and calculating n_{μ} for estimating the mean of $\ln(l/d)$:

$$n_{\mu} = \left[\frac{1.96 \times 0.746}{0.119} \right]^2 = 151.99 \approx 152$$

- 6) Taking $n_{\sigma^2, \mu} = \max(n_{\sigma^2}, n_{\mu}) = \max(210, 152) = 210$ as the required sample size.

If taking $E = 20\%$ $\bar{x} = 0.474$ instead of 5% \bar{x} , for matching with the n_{σ^2} estimate ($n_{\sigma^2} = 210$ is determined with s^2 is within 20% of σ^2), the n_{μ} is reduced from 152 to 10. This imply that n_{μ} is much smaller than n_{σ^2} at the same level of precision in the case of $\ln(l/d)$. In other words, the sample size could be determined so long as dealing with the variance.

CONCLUSIONS

1. All of the whiskers studied in this paper have the similar aspect ratio distribution density curve, the aspect ratio of different whiskers follow the same distribution model.
2. The aspect ratio of whiskers come from LN-Normal distribution population, particularly, “Kolmogorov - Smirnov Test” proves that the aspect ratio of four kinds of whiskers follow LN-Normal distribution at 0.99 level of confidence.
3. For evaluating the mean and the variance of whisker aspect ratio with 95% confidence and 20% error, 210 data should be randomly selected from the whisker aspect ratio population.

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